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Supporting Nepal's Low Carbon Pathway: Strategic Planning with OSeMOSYS

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Executive Summary:

Nepal has very low contribution to global GHG, the country is still committed to fighting climate change and had taken ambitious climate targets by using its renewable energy resource potential – mainly hydro and solar.

This study explores the scenarios with least cost for attainment of NDC 3.0 and Net Zero emissions targets set by Nepal. The study found that, if the emission limits are imposed and targets are achieved, there will be multiple direct co-benefits – lower energy demand, higher clean energy consumption, and economic savings in fossil fuel imports. The optimization model also suggests the cheapest energy mix for Nepal would be electricity from renewables and biomass.

However, achieving the targets would require high investments in power plant development as much a 7% of GDP. Nonetheless, with policies already in place, the supply system can be strong enough to cater the energy transition. Therefore, the governments main commotions will be first, to get additional financial supports for power sector development and secondly, formulate effective plans and polices to promote electrification in demand sectors and commercialization of biomass.

1. Introduction

Nepal is a landlocked country with no fossil fuel reserves but abundant renewable energy potential. This places Nepal in a position where it must rely on imported fuels while also having potential to meet demand through clean renewable energy. Nepal's emissions totals to about 38,211.96 Gg CO₂-eq , a tiny fraction of the global emissions (MoFE, 2025). Nevertheless, it is committed to climate action wherein NDC 3.0 targets a 26.79% emissions reduction by 2035 (Government of Nepal, 2025), and its long-term strategy aims for Net Zero carbon emission in overall by 2045 (MoFE, 2021a).

In case of Nepal, the power sector is already predominantly green, with over 3,591 MW from hydropower and solar PV by 2025 (MoEWRI, 2025a). Therefore, the key to achieving decarbonization lies in targeting the demand sectors. Following this need, the Government of Nepal has established an ambitious roadmap to develop 28,500 MW by 2035, (MoEWRI, 2025b), while NDC 3.0 committees for 15% generation by alternative renewable Energy by 2035.

Figure 1 Energy and emission situation of Nepal in 2022

2. Methodology

The baseline model has been developed with the energy balances published in Energy Synopsis reports of Nepal (WECS, 2023, 2024; MoF, 2025) while the energy generation and supply system has been calibrated using data from several reports (AEPC, 2022, 2024; NEA, 2022, 2023, 2024). The model was calibrated from the year 2022 till 2024 for energy demand and supply balance from these data. OSeMOSYS has been chosen to develop the energy system of Nepal. OSeMOSYS is a bottom-up linear programming model that identifies the optimum mix of the energy-technologies at the minimum cost under the constraints of GHG emission limitations, while fulfilling all the energy demands.

For the study, three scenarios have been evaluated based on the status and the major policies in place: Business-as-usual (BAU) scenario, NDC scenario and Net Zero Emissions (NZE) scenario as shown in Figure 2. The major assumptions are summarized below.

Business-as-usual (BAU) Scenario	NDC Scenario	NZE Scenario
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Energy demand growth based on economic factors •No Interventions on clean technology or emission reduction targets •Technology penetration go as trend 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Emission reduction target (17% in 2030, 27% in 2035) •100% Renewable electricity generation •10-15% alternative energy resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Add-on to NDC scenario •Attain 95% reduction in emissions by 2045

Figure 2 Scenario development for Nepal

- The BAU scenario assumes that the current trend of technology penetration and energy mix continues at the same pace as historical years. It explores the technology mix under no constraints on emissions, no intervention of higher rates of clean energy technologies.
- The NDC scenario¹ is based on the target of reducing emission by 17% by 2030 and 27% by 2035 and further years as compared to BAU scenario. The scenario also envisions the use of alternative energy resources up to 10% by 2030 and 15% by 2035 in the generation mix.

¹ Based on Nepal's Third Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC 3.0), 2025 (Government of Nepal, 2025)

- The NZE scenario² is built upon the NDC Scenario, but ambitious goal of limiting the emissions from energy sector below 95% level compared to BAU scenario. The Net zero target is achieved by carbon sequestration through forests and land use change.

3. Results:

Figure 3 indicates the CO₂ emission in each scenario. The scenario results verify that the CO₂ emission reduction targets can be met, given there is ample supply of electricity from renewable sources and use of clean energy. The results that, the best alternative for Nepal comes out to be use of carbon neutral biomass and electrification in short run as well as long run. With electrification of major activities using fossil fuels, using biomass as carbon neutral alternative for thermal purpose in industrial sector, and hydrogen for heavy freight vehicle in transport, the emission can be heavily reduced. The remaining emissions from energy sector is ought to be displaced by the sequestration by forest and land use change as indicated by Nepal’s LT-LEDS (MoFE, 2021b).

Figure 3 CO₂ emissions in BAU, NDC and NZE scenarios

The primary energy supply in BAU scenario is required to increase at the rate of 2.16%. However, due to switching to efficient technologies – mostly electrification, the energy supply requirement would grow at lower rates of 1.01% and 0.71% in NDC and NZE scenarios respectively (Figure 4). The effect of energy efficiency improvement is also seen at the final energy consumption level. It can be observed in the figures below that higher the emission limit, more the fossil fuels are cutoff. Therefore, all electricity generation are being from renewables in power sector, while in demand sector, the largest portion of the final energy demand is fulfilled by biomass for thermal purpose and electricity for all other purpose. The share of fossil fuel will decrease to about 15% and 2% in NDC and NZE scenario in 2050. The use of jet kerosene will continue to remain under the circumstances.

² Based on Long Term – Low Emission Development Strategies of Nepal, 2021

Figure 4 Total primary energy supply and final energy demand for BAU, NDC and NZE scenarios

To fulfil the electricity demand, the power plant capacity requirement also is higher than BAU scenario to 13.5 GW in NDC scenario and 14.9 GW in NZE scenario in 2050. The electricity supply will also increase accordingly, with highest being from hydropower while the supply from diesel plant and imports are avoided in both policy scenarios due to emission limitation as well higher cost of energy.

Figure 5 power plant capacity and electricity generation in BAU, NDC and NZE scenarios

Attaining the ambitious emission reduction goals comes with requirement of high investment costs in getting clean energy production and utilizing technologies. The total annualized investment cost required in developing electricity generation and supply system can reach up to as high as 7% and above in certain years (UN-CDP, 2025; World Bank, 2025). At an average annualized rate, it is almost 3% of GDP each year. These figures are very high than the global average of ~1.08% as of 2023 (IEA, 2023; World Bank, 2025). Therefore, it is crucial for Nepal to thoughtfully formulate policies and implement action strategies for get financial and technical aid from other sources including but not limited to climate financing, green funds or even direct foreign investment and so on.

(cumulative of 2022 to 2050, discounted to 2022)

Figure 6 Total costs in each scenario

Figure 7 compares each scenario in evaluation. It is observed that the highest emission reduction is achieved in NZE scenario followed by NDC, but to achieve the higher reduction, it requires higher total cost – mostly attributed to added investment costs. The marginal abatement cost for NDC and NZE scenario are about 170 USD/ton and 184 USD/ton respectively – the higher costs in NZE scenario are due to added cost of powerplant. Nonetheless, considering the total system cost, i.e. investment cost, fixed costs (representing operation and maintenance costs) and variable costs (representing operational costs including fuel costs), in long terms, the cumulative costs over the periods of 2022 to 2050 is lower in both policy scenarios. It is because there is decrease in cost of high costs related to import and use of fossil fuels as well import of electricity – thus result in net benefits due to fuel cost savings.

Figure 7 Emission vs total costs in each scenario

5. Discussion:

In the current situation, the only sector that needs decarbonization are the demand sectors, of which the industrial sector, transport sector and residential sector are the highest emitters of carbon dioxide (MoFE, 2025). Although the energy consumption in residential sector is highest (WECS, 2023), the emission in the residential sector is lowest, due to use of carbon neutral biomass, meanwhile that in industries is high pertaining to use of fossil fuels. Therefore, there is

an opportunity of repurposing the traditional use of biomass into commercial use in the industrial sector.

The analysis clearly indicates that attaining the NDC targets and NZE scenario are possible. With existing policies already in line such as Energy Development Roadmap with target of developing 6.6 GW and 13.5 GW of power plant capacity by 2030 and 2035 (MoEWRI, 2025b), the electricity generation capacity development plan in on its way to fulfil all the requirements for attaining the 2030 and 2035 targets of reaching NDC. This has a direct has direct impact in revenue generation within the country on one in one hand and in other savings in fuel import – given that the technologies are switched to electric systems. The net savings from energy imports alone accounts for net savings saving of nearly 23 billion USD in the period of 2022 to 2050.

The policy of Nepal also envisions integration of alternative renewable energy resources for electricity generation, which mostly includes solar and wind, which are variable renewable energy resources. However, due to the problem of grid flexibility, only 10-15% of total installed capacity is targeted. This system can play a vital role in redefining the consumer redefining consumer to a prosumer. However, due to its non-dispatchable nature, it is important to have a supporting system – primarily the battery storage system to support diurnal variability. Additionally, to accounts for seasonal variability, the detailed evaluation of pumped hydro energy storage system (PHES) is also looked upon as a good as good alternative. But since the model is driven by least cost, it did not account for the selection of PHES plant.

One of the import aspects of making policy to actions, financing, is the must. In that context, the high cost of renewable energy can be a hurdle. It is seen that the investment cost required for electricity generation and supply system can alone demand for 7% of GDP in some years. Nepal's Second NDCs as well as the Third NDCs indicate same hurdle and puts up high investment action targets as conditional targets (Government of Nepal, 2020, 2025). Therefore, Nepal should be able to capture the external support in form of climate finance, green funds, green bonds, and foreign direct investments.

Furthermore, to capitalize the lost cost due to traditional use of biomass, the products of forestry and agriculture should be promoted as commercial commodity – thus not only supporting the agroforestry but also helping the environment by keeping environment keeping it carbon neutral.

7. Conclusion:

Nepal, despite contributing only a negligible share to global emissions, has committed to emission reduction under international agreements. Unlike many countries, its power sector is already nearly carbon neutral due to heavy reliance on renewable energy, giving Nepal a strong starting position for decarbonization. However, future progress will depend on effective demand-side management through fuel switching, efficiency improvements, and adoption of advanced technologies, supported by a more robust supply system incorporating battery storage, pumped hydro, and potentially CCS - which require deeper analysis.

The energy model suggested the electrification and use of biomass to be the least cost mix of energy in case of Nepal – all electricity being generated from renewables. This would require 10GW of power plant capacity to be installed by 2035, which is luckily in line with government policy (MoEWRI, 2025b). Additionally, transmission capacity required is 8 GW by 2050, necessitating major system expansion and upgradation. Additional opportunities lie in

enhancing Nepal's energy security by reducing fossil fuel imports to only 2% from expected 32% in BAU scenario by 2050 — while also commercializing biomass for industrial thermal use and exploring hydrogen fuel for freight transport.

However, the investment requirements are significant, that can reach as high as 7% of GDP in some years (World Bank, 2023; UN-CDP, 2025), with an estimated 3% of GDP in average, compared to 2024 GDP. This is far above the global average of 1.08% (IEA, 2023). Therefore, government should focus on capturing financial supports from different available sources and create investment friendly environment.

In conclusion, achieving Nepal's Net Zero targets will require stringent action plans, effective policy implementation, regional collaboration, and global technical and financial support to overcome investment hurdles, ensure stability, and harness untapped opportunities for a clean and green economy.

Future study recommendations:

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| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Inclusion of detailed temporal demand pattern to study the scope of demand side management• Inclusion of detailed temporal variability of hydro electricity generation and possibility of integration of PHES• Implications of carbon tax on fuel switching and economic benefits |
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Appendices

Model Assumptions

- Only hydro, solar, wind and biomass usage for electricity generation (WECS, 2013; MoEWRI, 2025b)
- No natural gas for demand side as there is not infrastructure required for NGS and no government plans or polices on it.
- No CCS technologies as no plans and polices and studies have given proven feasibility.
- Residential cooking: use of solid fuels in residential cooking is limited to 30% by 2030; utilization of coal is limited to BAU scenario (NPC, 2017). This will be supported by penetration of electric stoves (MoEWRI, 2018).
- GDP of Nepal 2024: 42.9 billion USD (current price) (World Bank, 2025)
- Total costs = Investment costs + Fixed Costs + Variable/Fuel Costs
- For case of Nepal, the investment costs for electricity generation and supply systems are considered as total investment cost for power sector.

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